

DISSEMINATION OF PHYSICS LEARNING DEVICES BASED ON CREATIVE PROBLEM SOLVING MODEL INTEGRATED WITH SAVE ENERGY CHARACTER

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Abstract.

Creative problem solving (CPS) model can improve problem solving creativity. Creativity relates to the uniqueness and novelty of solutions used by students. Energy-saving characters need to be applied in learning so that students can face the energy crisis at this time. The purposes of this study were to see the practicality and effectiveness of learning devices that have been developed. The instruments of this research were practicality observation sheet, teacher and student response questionnaire, and essay sheet. This research phase was part of 4-D research and development model that was dissemination phase. The result of this research is the learning device based on CPS model integrated with the energy-saving character of obtaining the practical category (88,4) and effective (91,3).

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1. Introduction

The teaching materials used should meet the demands of the curriculum. The 2013 curriculum requires the formation of competencies (knowledge, skills, and attitudes) and character of students [1]. Character building is developed to answer the challenges of national life [2]. Character building is education related to character education by involving aspects of knowledge, attitudes and actions [3]. Thomas Lickona explained in his book that good character is doing good actions related to oneself and others [4].

Character building is prepared to deal with the nation's current problems [5]. One of the major problems facing this nation is the energy crisis. The use of energy resources in Indonesia 95.21% depends on fossils, while it is estimated that Indonesia's fossil energy sources will only last up to 12 years [6]. The availability of fossil fuels is depleting because it is used on a large scale. If Indonesia still relies on fossil energy sources, then oil reserves will decrease, oil prices will not be controlled, and pollution levels will increase [7]. The government needs to anticipate these problems. One of solutions that can be done is to instill energy-saving characters in students through integrated education in schools. In order to further strengthen the implementation of character education in education units 18 values have been identified derived from religion, Pancasila, culture and national education goals, namely: (1) Religious, (2) Honest, (3) Tolerance, (4) Discipline, (5) Hard work, (6) Creative, (7) Mandiri, (8) Democratic, (9) Curiosity, (10) Nationality, (11) Love of the Fatherland, (12) Appreciation of Achievement, (13) Friendly / Communicative, (14) Love of Peace, (15) Love of Reading, (16) Care for the Environment, (17) Social Care, (18) Responsibility [2]. While some attitudes that reflect energy-saving characters are like creative, meticulous, tolerant, and economical [7].

Learning tools that developed in addition to material in accordance with the curriculum, teaching materials also include renewable energy (biomass energy). This combination of materials uses the concept of fitting techniques [8]. This makes it possible to become human energy that is very economical in students [9]. The learning model used in learning is a Creative Problem Solving (CPS) model, because one of the styles used is a problem-solving solution. CPS can help students to improve students' creativity in solving problems [10]. CPS assists students in solving problems and thinking both in individual learning or in group learning [11]. CPS can help solve innovative and imaginative [12]. The CPS model applied in the learning tool is the CPS model proposed by Mitchel Kowalik which consists of the following steps: objective finding, fact finding, problem finding, idea finding, solution finding and acceptance findings [13].

2. Research Methode

This research was part of research and development with 4D-Model. 4D-Model consists of 4 steps: define, design, development, and dissemination [14]. Define stage was published in an article that published in prosiding SEMNAS UNP titled "Pengintegrasian Energi Terbarukan ke Dalam Perangkat Pembelajaran Fisika Berkarakter Hemat Energi - Model CPS dengan Pendekatan *Open-Ended* Menggunakan Analisis Dokumen" [15]. And then, design and develop phase have published in gravity journal titled 'Kualitas Perangkat Pembelajaran Fisika Berbasis Model Creative Problem Solving dengan Pendekatan Open-Ended pada Materi Usaha dan Energi Terintegrasi Energi Biomassa'. The results of development phase were physics-based instructional device of creative problem solving model with open-ended approach on work and energy materials integrated by biomass energy can be used in physics learning in the high school because learning devices have good criteria (valid, practical, and effective) [9]. Dissemination can be done if the product (learning device) developed is valid according to the expert, practical and effective when used in learning. Dissemination is the stage of using learning tools that have been developed on a larger scale, for example in other classes, in other schools, or by other teachers. The purpose of this dissemination is to test the practicality and effectiveness of using the device in the learning process. Instrument used in this research were questionnaire, essay test, observation sheets, self-assessment and peers the assessment sheet. This research was done in SMAN 7 Padang. This research is helped by some observer.

3. Results

3.1. Practical Test

There were some measurement which was conducted to see practicality of learning devices. First, the implementation of the learning implementation plan (RPP) uses an observation sheet whose contents are in accordance with the learning stage in the RPP. The result of measurement can be seen in Table 1:

Table 1. Implementation of RPP

Meeting	Score	Category
First	94.74	Implemented
Second	92.11	Implemented
third	90.79	Implemented

fourth	97.37	Implemented
fifth	93,42	Implemented
sixth	98.68	Implemented
seventh	100	Implemented

Based on Table 1 seen that the learning steps developed in the lesson plan have been implemented in the learning process. This is evidenced by the acquisition of the average value for each RPP implementation of 95.30.

Next, to measure practicality of learning tools (Student Worksheet and Handout) using questionnaire. The datas are presented in Table 2:

Table 2: Student Respos for handout and LKS

No	Statements	Handout		Student worksheet	
		Score	%	Score	%
1	By using biomass energy integrated material handouts and student worksheet, it is easy to understand material facts, concepts, principles and procedures	3.33	83.33	3.5	87.5
2	Handouts and student worksheet quickly understand the facts, concepts, principles and procedures of the material	3.38	84.38	3.42	85.42
3	Handouts and student worksheet satisfied for the facts, concepts, principles and procedures of the material	3.29	82.29	3.5	87.5
4	Questions in handouts/student worksheet can lead me to find an integrated concept of biomass energy	3.38	84.38	3.33	83.33
5	Handouts and student worksheets are interesting to learn	3.42	85.42	3.33	83.33
6	Handout and student worksheet are interested to read	3.29	82.29	3.46	86.46
7	Problems in handouts and student worksheet can be done well	3.25	81.25	3.29	82.29
8	Problems in integrated handouts and student worksheets are simple and interesting biomass energy to learn	3.42	89.58	3.5	87.5
Average		3.36	84.11	3.43	85.83

Based on Table 2, we can see that handout and student worksheets are practice to use in learning process, the average score of handout and student worksheet tare 84,11 and 85,33. Both are in the practical category.

3.2. Effectiveness

3.2.1. Knowledge Competence

Based on the analysis carried out, the scores obtained by students were in the range of 66 to 95 with an average of 83. There were 2 students who had grades below the established standard of 75. The classical completeness of this learning got a score of 91.3%. In general, learning devices and integrated energy of biomass energy have been completed. Learning devices developed are effective to help students achieve learning objectives.

3.2.2. *Insight of Saving Energy Character*

Assessment of energy-saving characters includes creative, careful, tolerant and economical. The following is a graph of the increase in the saving energy character of students based on the observation:

Based on Figure 1, it can be seen that there is an increase in creative character as a form of energy-saving character at each meeting. The value for each creative character ranges from 65.63 to 82.99. Based on Figure 2, it was seen that there was an increase in careful character for each meeting. The value for each meeting ranges from 63.19 to 82.63. Based on Figure 3, it is seen that there is an increase in Tolerance character for each meeting. The value for each meeting ranges from 63.19 to 82.63. Based on Figure 4 it can be seen that there is a development of tolerance character for each meeting. The score for each meeting is in the range of 62.5 to 83.1. These characters evolve from categories starting to develop into habits. Figure 4 illustrates an increase

in economical character. This saving character develops from a score of 73.61 to 90.28. In other words, the students' character of energy increases from categories starts from develop into habits. Based on the analysis that has been carried out for character evaluation in general, it has increased from category to developing into a habit. The results of statistical tests obtained by the characters of each meeting increased with the value of $r = 0.981$. This shows that there is an increase in character values at each meeting. On the other hand, the relationship of the value with the increase in character value was $r = 0.08$. This shows that increasing the character value at each meeting was not accompanied by an increase in the character value.

3.2.3. Problem Solving Skill

In Table 3 an assessment of students' skills in solving problems will be presented. The aspects assessed are adjusted according to the steps of the CPS model used. Assessment of problem solving skills based on worksheets done by students.

Table 3: Score students' ability to solve problems

No	The measured aspect	Score
1	Students identify objects to be studied,	79.56
2	Students identify situations that provide problems,	79.96
3	Students identify all data relating to the object to be discussed	85.41
4	Students identify information related to the object to be discussed	81.45
5	Students identify problems	82.63
6	Students are able to send creative questions related to the problem	80.45
7	Students are able to develop new ideas regarding problem solving,	80.85
8	Students are able to get ideas about problem solving	81.15
9	Students are able to make a list of solutions regarding the problems given	83.63
10	Students are able to apply the list of solutions found at the stage of idea finding to solve the given problem,	83.23
11	Students are able to make final conclusions regarding the problem given.	83.93
Average		82,02

Based on Table 3, it can be seen that the overall average for problem solving skills is 82.02. Learning tools are effective when used to develop problem solving skills

4. Discuss

The results of the practicality test at the dissemination stage are in a very practical category. This is evidenced by observing the implementation of RPP and student responses. The learning steps developed in the RPP have been implemented with a score of 95.30. Student responses have also been in a very practical category with an average score of 84.11 for handouts and 85.83 for practicality of LKS. Based on the results of the analysis it can be concluded that the practical learning tools developed are used in different classes. This is in accordance with the opinion of Arikunto and Jabar [16]. Which states that an instrument meets practical criteria when it is easy to use and not complicated [16].

The results of the effectiveness analysis show that students have reached 75% of the learning objectives set. Then the character of energy saving students has increased from the category began

to develop to become a habit. This is due to the influence of biomass integration as a regional potential for character formation. [16]. In addition, the competence of students' skills to solve problems also increases for each meeting, because the development of teaching materials is carried out according to the steps of the CPS model. The CPS model is a methodological step that can lead to problem solving [11].

5. Conclusion

The dissemination result of learning devices were obtained by learning tools integrated of biomass energy based on the CPS model with an open-ended approach that was practical and effective when distributed in other classes. The average test of the practicality of the learning device was 83.41 with a very practical category and the effectiveness of the device was at a score of 91.30. Learning tools developed are suitable for distribution to other schools.

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